

Job Performance and Satisfaction of Job Order Employees at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology

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Abstract:- Every organization consists of tangible and intangible elements: the environment, vision and mission, values, objectives, strategies, authorities, work, people and other resources (land, labor, capital, entrepreneurship and technology, especially ICT). The only living thing among these elements is the human beings, who have entered into a contractual relationship with the organization to offer their human endowments in exchange for some forms of rewards”. People stay or leave the company for more reasons they are satisfied with their job promotional opportunity and work environment. This study aims to determine job order employees' job performance and job satisfaction in Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, Cabanatuan City. The study used a descriptive research design that used a survey questionnaire to solicit data on the profile of respondents and to determine the respondents' job performance and job satisfaction. Analysis of the resulting survey data included descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and weighted mean. The study consisted of 40 job order employees from Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, General Tinio Street Campus, Cabanatuan City. The majority of them or, 29 (72.50%), were male, more than half or 25 (62.50%) had an age between 21 to 30 and a half or 20 (50.00%) were college graduates. Many of them or 38 (95.00%) do not have civil service eligibility and 21 (52.50%) were single and half of them do not have any dependents. The majority of them perform clerical functions in the institution. Regarding their job performance, in general, all of them often perform the work values: being hardworking, cooperative, responsible, attentive, able to work under pressure, can meet deadlines, and effective in their job. Last, many of the respondents were not satisfied with their job. For the conclusions, an employee under the job order program of the government was doing and giving their best in their job. Their work values, regardless of what function they do in the institution, were better. However, as the price of basic commodities increases, an increased monthly wage is also needed. With this, the employee may feel dissatisfied,

not because of the institution or management, but merely because of the situation they are experiencing of.

Keywords:- Job Performance, Job Satisfaction, Job Order Employee.

I. INTRODUCTION

Every organization consists of tangible and intangible elements: the environment, vision and mission, values, objectives, strategies, authorities, work, people and other resources (land, labor, capital, entrepreneurship and technology, especially ICT). The only living thing among these elements is the human beings, who have entered into a contractual relationship with the organization to offer their human endowments in exchange for some forms of rewards” (1). Some forms of rewards talking in terms of what will be referred to in law as consideration and in a simple term as wage or salary.

Payment of wage or salary to employees by the employer is mandatory by law but not just for its fun. It must be noted that such wage or salary paid is an instrument of motivation or ‘driver’ for the workforce to keep body and soul together and possibly make them stakeholders in the organization. It is common knowledge that when you are a stakeholder in an organization, such an employee will always want the survival of such organization at all times. This is one of the challenges of motivation within organizations. Motivation is one of the most significant challenges facing managers across the globe because it influences workers’ performance and, thus, the extent to which organizations can achieve their objectives and justify their existence (2).

Cummings (1978), cited by (3), argued that the management of human resources is “concerned with obtaining the best staff for an organization, and having got them, looking after them so that they will stay and give of their best to their jobs”. This is pointing to the fact that proper recruitment process must be strictly adhered to, as ascertained in (4);

recruitment process in the organization and after getting the best staff, the next thing is looking after them so that they will stay to give their best in terms of their input for optimal organizational development.

The use of temporary workers or sometimes called job order employees, is growing rapidly. It has spread across industries—from manufacturing to services and other occupations, including construction workers, registered nurses, bankers, information technologists. The number of companies using temporary workers increased as global competition increased and the urge to cut down on costs of undertaking businesses to remain competitive rises (5).

Short-term employment is perceived as resulting from continuous changes in the working arrangement worldwide and has become a key concern in the last three decades (6). Some firms use the short-term employment condition as a pseudo-probationary period to preview workers from whom they screen out those who fail to meet performance criteria or do not otherwise “fit” the organization or extend an offer of long-term employment to desired individuals (7).

The value of employee training as compensation and benefits packages has increased the performance human resource outcomes increases typically the performance, satisfaction and productivity also stay there and attracting. The perception of employees about the organization benefits policy. Suppose pay is tied to employee performance, good quality and quantity of work done (8). Organizational pay directly influences voluntary employee turnover compared to their pay available in other organizations (9). People stay or leave the company for more reasons. They are satisfied with their job promotional opportunity and work environment (10). With this, the researchers want to determine the job performance and job satisfaction of job order employees in Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, Cabanatuan City

Objectives

This study aims to determine the job performance and satisfaction of job order employees in Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, Cabanatuan City

Specifically, the researchers desire to gain answers on the following objectives:

1. Describe the profile of the respondents in terms of their sex, age, educational attainment, civil service eligibility, civil status, number of dependents and nature of employment.
2. Describe the job performance of job order employees based on their work values, including being hardworking, cooperative, responsible, attentive, able to work under pressure, can meet deadlines, and efficient in their job.
3. Determine the job satisfaction of job order employees.

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ *Research Design*

The study used a descriptive research design that used a survey questionnaire to solicit data on the profile of respondents and to determine the respondents’ job performance and satisfaction Analysis of the resulting survey data included descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages and weighted mean.

➤ *Locale of the Study*

This study was conducted at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, General Tinio Street Campus, located at Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija, during School Year 2020 – 2021.

➤ *Respondents of the Study*

The study respondents were the job order employees from the different Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology offices, General Tinio Street Campus in School Year 2020-2021.

➤ *Sampling and Sampling Procedure*

The study respondents were the job order employees from the different offices of Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, General Tinio Street Campus. Purposive sampling was used since only those with Messenger and Internet connections were chosen to be the respondents.

➤ *Research Instrument*

This section was composed of three parts—first, the survey questionnaire for the respondent's profile. Second, the job performance of the respondent based on their work values and last, the satisfaction of the respondents in their current job.

To describe the job performance of the respondents, the respondents were given five options in evaluating/ rating their job performance based on their work value, as follows:

Scale	Verbal Interpretation
5	Always
4	Often
3	Seldom
2	Rarely
1	Never

The ratings in the questionnaire were interpreted using the here underscoring guide:

Units of the Indexes	Adjective Description
4.21 to 5.00	Always
3.41 to 4.20	Often
2.61 to 3.40	Seldom
1.81 to 2.60	Rarely
1.01 to 1.80	Never

➤ *Data Gathering and Procedure*

The first step in the data collection process was to ask permission from the Director of each campus of Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology. After the approval, the researcher administered the survey questionnaire through the use of Google Form.

➤ *Ethical form of Consideration*

Permission was sought from the Director of each campus. Informed consent was given first before the respondent answered the questionnaire. Sufficient time was given to ask questions, and the anonymity of the subjects and confidentiality of information was maintained.

➤ *Methods of Data Analysis*

The following statistical methods were used:

1. Frequency counts, percentages and weighted mean were utilized to describe respondents' profiles and determine their job performance and satisfaction.

III. RESULTS

The data obtained were organized, analyzed, and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools such as frequency count, percentage and weighted mean.

A. Profile of the Respondent

Table 1. Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency(F)	Percentage (%)
Male	29	72.50
Female	11	27.50
Total	40	100%

Table 1 shows the sex of the respondent. Out of 40, 29 or 72.50% were male while 11 or 27.50 % were female.

Table 2. Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Below 21	2	5.00
21 to 30	25	62.50
31 to 40	8	20.00
41 to 50	5	12.50
Total	40	100%

Table 2 shows the age of the respondents. Out of 40, 25 or 62.50% age was between 21 to 30, 8 or 20.00% was between 31 to 40, 5 or 12.50% was 41 to 50 and 2 or 5.00% was below 21 years old. .

Table 3. Educational Attainment of the Respondents

Educational Attainment	Frequency(F)	Percentage (%)
College	20	50.00
High School	17	42.50
Elementary	3	7.50
Total	40	100%

Table 3 shows the educational attainment of the respondents. Out of 40, 20 or 50.00% was college graduate, 17 or 42.50% was high school graduate and 3 or 7.50% was elementary graduate.

Table 4. Civil Service Eligibility of the Respondents

Civil Service Eligibility	Frequency(F)	Percentage (%)
With Eligibility	2	5.00
Without Eligibility	38	95.00
Total	40	100%

Table 4 shows the civil service eligibility of the respondents. Out of 40, 38 or 95.00% do not have civil service eligibility while 2 or 5.00% have civil service eligibility.

Table 5. Civil Status of the Respondents

Civil Status	Frequency(F)	Percentage (%)
Single	21	52.50
Married	19	47.50
Total	40	100%

Table 5 shows their civil status. Out of 40, 21 or 52.50% were single while 19 or 47.50% were married.

Table 6. Number of Dependents of the Respondents

Civil Status	Frequency(F)	Percentage (%)
0	20	50.00
1	2	5.00
2	8	20.00
3	3	7.50
4	3	7.50
5	3	7.50
6	1	2.50
Total	40	100%

Table 6 shows the number of dependents of the respondents. Out of 40, 20 or 50.00% do not have any dependents, 8 or 20.00% have two dependents, 3 or 7.50% have three, four and five dependents, 2 or 5.00% have 1 dependent and 1 or 2.50% have six dependents.

Table 7. Nature of Employment of the Respondents

Civil Status	Frequency(F)	Percentage (%)
Clerical	19	47.50
Utility	14	35.00
Security	7	17.50
Total	40	100%

Table 7 shows the nature of employment of the respondents. Out of 40, 19 or 47.50% perform clerical functions, 14 or 35.00% perform utility functions and 7 or 17.50% perform security functions.

B. Job Performance of the Job Order Employees based on Their Work Values

Table 8. Job Performance of the Respondents Performing Clerical Functions

Work Values	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
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Hardworking	3.47	Often
Job Effectiveness	3.37	Seldom
Meeting Deadlines	3.21	Seldom
Cooperative	3.84	Often
Responsible	3.89	Often
Able To Work Under Pressure	3.16	Seldom
Attentive	3.84	Often
Average Weighted Mean	3.54	Often

Table 8 shows the performance of the respondents performing clerical functions. Based on the result, the data showed that the respondents who had clerical functions were often hardworking, cooperative, responsible, and attentive while seldom working under pressure, meeting deadlines, and being effective in their job. Being responsible garnered the highest weighted mean, equivalent to 3.89 with verbal interpretation “Often.” Also, working under pressure got the lowest weighted mean, which is equivalent to 3.16 with verbal interpretation “Seldom.” The average weighted mean obtained is 3.54 with a verbal interpretation of “Often.”

Table 9. Job Performance of the Respondents Performing Utility Functions

Work Values	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Hardworking	3.93	Often
Job Effectiveness	3.21	Seldom
Meeting Deadlines	4.14	Often
Cooperative	3.79	Often
Responsible	3.36	Seldom
Able To Work Under Pressure	3.64	Often
Attentive	3.07	Seldom
Average Weighted Mean	3.59	Often

Table 9 shows the performance of the respondents performing utility functions. Based on the result, the data showed that the respondents who had utility functions were often hardworking, cooperative, and able to work under pressure and can meet deadlines while they were seldom attentive, able to work under pressure, responsible, and effective in their job. Can meet deadlines garner the highest weighted mean, which is equivalent to 4.14 with verbal interpretation “Often.” Also, being attentive got the lowest weighted mean, equivalent to 3.07 with verbal interpretation “Seldom.” The average weighted mean obtained is 3.59 with a verbal interpretation of “Often.”

Table 10. Job Performance of the Respondents Performing Security Functions

Work Values	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Hardworking	3.57	Often
Job Effectiveness	3.71	Often
Meeting Deadlines	3.57	Often

Cooperative	3.86	Often
Responsible	3.86	Often
Able To Work Under Pressure	4.57	Always
Attentive	3.86	Often
Average Weighted Mean	3.86	Often

Table 10 shows the performance of the respondents performing security functions. Based on the result, the data showed that the respondents, who had security functions, were always able to work under pressure and were often hardworking, cooperative, could meet deadlines, attentive, responsible and effective in their job. Can able to work under pressure garner the highest weighted mean, which is equivalent to 4.57 with verbal interpretation “Always.” Also, being hardworking and can meet deadlines got the lowest weighted mean, which is equivalent to 3.07 with verbal interpretation “Often.” The average weighted mean obtained is 3.86 with a verbal interpretation of “Often.”

C. Job Satisfaction of the Respondents

Table 11. Job Satisfaction of the Respondents

Civil Service Eligibility	Frequency(F)	Percentage (%)
Satisfied	19	47.50
Not Satisfied	21	52.50
Total	40	100%

Table 11 shows the job satisfaction of the respondents. Based on the result, the data showed that the majority of 21 or 52.50% of the respondents were not satisfied while only 19, or 47.50% were satisfied with their job.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this study, three objectives were established to explain the job order employees' job performance and job satisfaction. The first objective was to describe the study population. According to the profile of the respondents, the majority of them were male, had an age between 21 to 30, and were college graduates. Many of them do not have civil service eligibility and are single. The majority of them do not have any dependents and perform a clerical function in the institution.

The employment rate was higher among men compared to women. In April 2020, most of the employed persons were in the age group 25 to 34 years old, followed by the employed persons in the age group 35 to 44 years old, and in the age group 45 to 54 years old (11). One way to earn civil service eligibility is to pass the Civil Service Examination. However, in the past years, the passing rate in Civil Service Examination has been low. In August 2019, only 11.62% or 29,733 examinees out of a total of 255,778 takers of the CSC career service test passed. Some 290,000 people were supposed to take the CSC pen-and-paper test last March 2020, which was reset to 2021 due to the pandemic (12). The overall dependency ratio of the Philippines was 61, which indicates that for every 100 working-age population, there were about 61 dependents (13).

The second objective was to describe the job performance of the respondents. The average weighted mean obtained for clerical functions is equivalent to 3.54, which has a verbal interpretation of "Often." Clerical work refers to daily office duties, such as data entry, answering phone calls, and sorting and filing documents. Clerical duties are often found in different types of administrative and office support roles. Usually, clerical duties are performed by office clerks, and secretaries, and sometimes, administrative assistants and clerks must know how to use sophisticated computer systems, copiers, printers, and other equipment to carry out many clerical duties (14). Because of the nature of the work of those in clerical functions, most of the work values were seen often. Furthermore, those with utility functions also obtained an average weighted mean equivalent to 3.59, which has a verbal interpretation of "Often". Utility workers or utility functions in an institution are responsible for cleaning and maintaining company premises and equipment. Their job is to keep upkeep of the company's facilities, repair broken equipment, inspect finished projects, and comply with state health and safety regulations (15). Being hardworking tops, the list of the work values possessed by utility workers because of the nature of their work. Last, those with security functions also obtained an average weighted mean equivalent to 3.86, which has a verbal interpretation of "Often". A security guard or those who have security functions protect and enforce laws on an employer's property, monitor alarms and closed-circuit TV cameras, control access for employees, visitors, and outside contractors, conduct security checks over a specified area, write comprehensive reports outlining what they observed while on patrol and detain criminal violators. They must remain alert, looking for anything out of the ordinary throughout their shift. In an emergency, guards may call for assistance from police, fire, or ambulance services (16). In general, all of the respondents often perform the work values: being hardworking, cooperative, responsible, attentive, able to work under pressure, can meet deadlines, and being effective in their job.

The third objective was to determine the job satisfaction of the respondents. Based on the result, more respondents were not satisfied (52.50%) than those satisfied (47.50%). Some employees leave their jobs for better opportunities, while others choose to stay and remain unhappy. One of the primary reasons for job dissatisfaction is the minimum wage they earned which is not enough for daily living. Not only must employees deal with stagnant wages but perhaps also the high cost of health insurance and rising costs for housing, utilities, and food. The stress of paying bills with limited income causes many workers to feel dissatisfied with their jobs (17). Since the commitment towards the organization can be in three different aspects personal, service, and career (18).

V. CONCLUSION

At present, an employee under the job order program of the government was doing and giving their best in their job. Their work values, regardless of what function they do in the institution, were better. However, as the price of basic commodities increases, the need for an increased monthly

wage is also needed. With this, the employee may feel dissatisfied, not because of the institution or management, but merely because of the situation, they are experiencing.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Muo, I. (2013). Motivating & Manageing Knowledge Workers: Evidences from Diverse Industries & Cultures. *J. Mgmt. & Sustainability*, 3, 119.
- [2]. Sule, O. E., Amuni, S. I., Obasan, K. A., & Banjo, H. A. (2015). Wages and salaries as a motivational tool for enhancing organizational performance. a survey of selected Nigerian workplace. *EuroEconomica*, 34(1).
- [3]. Bello, M. F., & Isa, M. K. (2015). Recruitment Policy and its Effect on Staff Performance in Toro Local Government Area of Bauchi State. *Kaduna Journal of Sociology*, 3(1), 35-52.
- [4]. Sule, O. E., & Elizabeth, U. I. (2013). Impact of personal recruitment on organisational development: A survey of selected Nigerian workplace. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 4(2), 79.
- [5]. Wandera, H. T. (2011). The effects of short term employment contract on an organization: A case of Kenya Forest Service. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 1(21), 184-204.
- [6]. Gabagambi, Jovin Peter and Wei, Song (2018). Impacts of short term employment contract on employee performance: A case study of government organizations in Tanzania. *American International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences*. ISSN (Print): 2328-3734, ISSN (Online): 2328-3696, ISSN (CD-ROM): 2328-3688
- [7]. Druker, J., Croucher, R. (2000), "National collective bargaining and employment flexibility in the European building and civil engineering industries", *Construction Management and Economics*, Vol. 18 No.4, pp.699-709.
- [8]. Ivancevich, John M. William F. Glueck. (1989). *Foundations of Personnel/Human Management*. 21397-409.
- [9]. Heneman, Hebert G., Donald P. Schwab, John A. Fossum, Lee D. Dyer. (1987).
- [10]. Mitchell, Terence R. Brooks C. Holtom, Thomas W. Lee. (1993). *How to Keep Your Werther*, Williams B. and Davis, Keith. (1996). *Human resource and Personnel management*. New York: McGraw Hill, Inc
- [11]. Philippine Statistics Authority. (2021, September). *Employment Situation in April 2020*. <https://psa.gov.ph/statistics/survey/labor-and-employment/labor-force-survey/title/Employment%20Situation%20in%20April%202020>
- [12]. ABS-CBN News. (2020, November 11). CSC mulls lowering passing rate for civil service exams. <https://news.abs-cbn.com/news/11/11/20/csc-mulls-lowering-passing-rate-for-civil-service-exams>.
- [13]. The age and sex structure of the Philippine population: (Facts from the 2010 census) | Philippine Statistics Authority. (n.d.). <https://psa.gov.ph/content/age-and-sex-structure-philippine-population-facts-2010-census>.
- [14]. Indeed Editorial Team. (2020, February 25). Clerical definition (Plus common clerical duties). *Indeed Career*

- Guide. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/clerkal-duties>.
- [15]. Utility worker job description. (2020, November 15). Betterteam. <https://www.betterteam.com/utility-worker-job-description>.
- [16]. What does a security guard do? (2018, August 28). CareerExplorer. <https://www.careerexplorer.com/careers/security-guard/>
- [17]. Johnson, Rose. (2018, November). Key reasons for job dissatisfaction and poor employee performance. Small Business - Chron.com. <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/key-reasons-job-dissatisfaction-poor-employee-performance-25846.html>
- [18]. Santos, A. R. (2020). Organizational commitment of instructors of private colleges in Nueva Ecija. International Journal of Humanities and Education Development (IJHED), 2(1), 57-60.